

STUDY OF THE LONGITUDINAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES USING VARIOUS CLASSICAL AND INNOVATIVE TESTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

F. Laurin¹, A. Mavel¹, J. Berthe¹, C. Huchette¹

¹Onera, Paris-Saclay University
29 avenue de la division Leclerc, 932322 Chatillon France
Email: frederic.laurin@onera.fr, web page: <http://www.onera.fr>

Keywords: Fibre, Ply, Strength, Analytical modelling, Mechanical testing, Thermal analysis

ABSTRACT

In the design of aeronautical structures, determining the allowable values associated with failure criteria remains a key issue for the aeronautical industry, particularly the longitudinal compressive strength. Furthermore, this critical allowable value must be determined at various temperatures representative of flight conditions, or even in the event of a fire, which adds complexity to the multi-instrumented testing procedure and the associated analysis methods. This study has determined the longitudinal compressive strength of T700GC/M21 unidirectional carbon/epoxy plies by considering different classical and innovative tests performed at various temperatures (from ambient to 120 °C) and analysing them using an original hybrid failure approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials, especially carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP), are widely used in modern aircraft. Currently, design methods for laminated composite structures mainly rely on linear elastic structural analysis combined with failure criteria [1] defined at the scale of the unidirectional (UD) ply. Therefore, determining the design allowable — the ply strengths that take into account material scattering, as recommended in aeronautical standards [2]— is a major concern for designers. Determining the design allowable is a time-consuming and expensive process since many tests are required, especially at different temperatures representative of flight or fire conditions. To reduce costs and product lead times, fast and simple identification tests and analysis methods are required. Furthermore, identifying tests with low coefficients of variation (CV) would increase the A- and B-basis allowable [2], resulting in higher-performance designs. Among the in-plane strengths of a unidirectional ply, determining the longitudinal compressive strength of the ply currently remains a technical and scientific challenge.

This article analyses existing tests for determining the longitudinal compressive strength of unidirectional plies at different temperatures, from ambient temperature to 120°C. It considers classical compressive tests described in Section 2.1, but also classical and innovative bending tests in sections 3.1 and 3.2. An approach based on failure analysis has been developed to predict fibre kinking in composite laminates subjected to different loadings and temperatures in section 2.2. This approach considers the unidirectional ply as the elementary modelling entity, but some material parameters are updated using a micromechanical model. The model is applied to different test configurations performed at various temperatures in compression (section 2.3) and bending (section 3.3).

2 COMPRESSION TESTS ON UD PLY AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

2.1 Presentation of compression test results on UD ply

The longitudinal compressive strength of carbon/epoxy T700GC/M21 unidirectional plies (aeronautical quality) with a weight area of 268 g/m² has been determined using classical compression tests on 16 0° laminates. All composite specimens were manufactured at ONERA using an autoclave, with a curing cycle corresponding to that recommended by the material provider.

The longitudinal compressive strength, associated with the onset of fibre kinking, is usually identified using standards based on uniaxial compressive tests on unidirectional 0° laminates. There are many standards regarding testing methods and fixtures in the literature. As initially proposed by [3] and subsequently refined in ASTM D3410/D3410M-16 [4], compressive force can be transferred to the specimen via shear at the wedge grip interfaces. This experimental device requires the use of tabbed specimens and complex, heavy fixtures. Alternatively, the EN2850 AECMA standard [5] recommends transmitting the compressive force into the specimen through end-loading [6], thus avoiding the use of additional tabs. [5] recommends transmitting the compressive force into the specimen through end-loading [6], thus avoiding the need for additional tabs. This method is currently the most commonly used in the aeronautical industry and corresponds to the ASTM D695-15 standard [7]. Finally, the ASTM D6641/D6641M standard [8] combines shear and end-loading to transmit the compressive force.

Since a higher compressive strength can be obtained using the latter method [9,10], the experimental device shown in Fig. 1 has been considered in the present study. It is associated with an Instron hydraulic testing machine with a maximum load capacity of 300 kN. Compression tests were performed at ONERA Lille with a loading rate of 1.5 mm/s. Longitudinal strain was measured using a QFLAB-3-11 strain gauge. The experimental device was introduced into a furnace, as illustrated in Fig. 1b. Compression tests have been carried out at four different temperatures: 20 °C, 80 °C, 100 °C and 120 °C. Three specimens were tested for each configuration of tests to estimate the scattering.

Figure 1: a) compression test device available at ONERA, b) compression test performed in a furnace.

Fig. 2a shows that the behaviour in the fibre direction appears to be insensitive to the applied temperature and exhibits slight nonlinearity up to failure. Experimental results have already demonstrated that this nonlinearity is due to the nonlinear elastic behaviour imposed by the carbon fibres [11,12], which is consistent with the observations performed in this study. Fig. 2b shows the evolution of the measured longitudinal compressive strength as a function of temperature. The evolution is almost linear and consequent (the strength is decreased by 40% at 120°C). It should be noted that the scatter of the measured strength increases with temperature. The failure patterns of the different specimens, as shown in Fig. 2b, are not located at the ends of the jaws, and the tests appear to be relevant for measuring the longitudinal compressive strength at different temperatures using the proposed experimental device.

Figure 2: a) Longitudinal behavior and b) evolution of the longitudinal compressive strength of UD ply subjected to compression loading at different temperatures

2.2 Micromechanical model to predict the longitudinal compressive strength of a UD ply

A model defined at the micromechanical scale has been proposed by Grandidier [13,14]. This model is based on finite element simulations with enhanced elements to capture the fibre buckling embedded within the matrix. Based on this work, a simplified analytical model has been proposed by Grandidier [15] later in order to be used in design office to determine the longitudinal compressive strength, considering compressive loading or bending. The model accounting for the combined contributions of fibre micro-buckling [16] and the structural effect (stacking sequence, strain gradient) [17–19] was proposed to describe the mechanism of failure under compression or flexural loading [15]. The local failure mechanism accepted by the scientific community puts together a sequence of phenomena: under compression load a little fibre misalignment triggers fibre buckling, the matrix provides the assembly of the fibres but evolves to plasticity which amplifies therefore the instability, fibre failure appears successively by developing a kink band [16]. The main governing parameters of this mechanism are the nonlinearity of matrix properties and fibres initial undulation defects noted ϕ_0 .

The most efficient models existing in the literature account quite well for these effects. Budiansky and Fleck [16] modelled the non-linear shear behaviour of UD (shear strain) vs. (shear stress) by using a Ramberg-Osgood (RO) description, reported in Eq. 1:

$$\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_{UD}^y} = \frac{\tau}{\tau_{UD}^y} + \frac{3}{7} \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{UD}^y} \right)^{n_{UD}} \quad (1)$$

It involves three material parameters (τ_{UD}^y , G_{UD} , n_{UD}) or (γ_{UD}^y , τ_{UD}^y , n_{UD}). G_{UD} is the in-plane shear modulus of the composite, τ_{UD}^y is a nominal shear yield stress for which the secant modulus is reduced to 70% of its initial value G_{UD} . γ_{UD}^y is defined as the elastic strain at the shear stress τ_{UD}^y so that $\tau_{UD}^y = G_{UD} \cdot \gamma_{UD}^y$. The compressive strength, referred to as σ_{UD}^{stab} , and calculated using Budiansky and Fleck's model, is defined as the maximum stress applied on UD before the fibre instability, as reported in Eq. 2.

$$\sigma_{UD}^{stab} = \frac{1}{1 + n_{UD} \left(\frac{3}{7} \right)^{\frac{1}{n_{UD}}} \left(\frac{\phi_0 / \gamma_{UD}^y}{n_{UD} - 1} \right)^{\frac{n_{UD} - 1}{n_{UD}}}} \quad (2)$$

The structural effect results in the increase of UD failure compressive strain and stress with respect to σ_{UD}^{stab} . It is due to several mechanisms that do not take place at the UD mesoscopic scale but rather at a larger, macroscopic scale (laminate).

Three factors are included in the structural effect, namely the deformation gradient through the thickness due to bending loadings, the thickness of UD ply and the stiffness of off-axis neighbouring plies. Experimental observations on the structural effect have been experimentally detailed and compared by Grandidier [15], ending with the proposal of an analytical model (reported in Eq. 3) to predict the stress due to structural application.

$$\sigma_{UD}^{struct} = 2r_{gf} \frac{\pi}{e_b} \sqrt{\frac{E_m E_f}{1 - \nu_m^2} V_f (1 - V_f)} \quad (3)$$

where r_{gf} is the gyration radius of fibre $r_{gf} = I/S$, with I the second moment of area of the fibre, and S the area of the fibre's cross section (it is equivalent to the fibre diameter divided by 4, in case of fibres are considered circular), E_m and ν_m are respectively the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the matrix, E_f the longitudinal elastic modulus of the fibre, V_f the volume fraction of fibres and e_b the characteristic thickness of UD involved in the instability mode (a fraction of the total thickness of UD), which is discussed below. For a UD layer subjected to bending, only the part in compression is considered for critical thickness (e_c). A reduced part of thickness is considered to contribute to compression failure due to the distribution of the strain and is considered equal to $e_b = 0.5 e_c$ which permits correlation with experimental results considering the evolution of the middle plan during bending loading because the longitudinal behaviour in tension and in compression is different. For a UD layer subjected to compression, $e_b = \infty$ to deactivate the structural part in the model.

To summarize, the proposed model considers both the micro-buckling mechanism (σ_{UD}^{stab}) and the structural effect (σ_{UD}^{struct}). The estimated compressive strength is called critical, referred to as σ_{UD}^{crit} , is higher than σ_{UD}^{stab} , since it is defined in Eq. 4:

$$\sigma_{UD}^{crit} = \sigma_{UD}^{stab} + \sigma_{UD}^{struct} \quad (4)$$

2.3 Analysis of compression tests with an advanced micromechanical model

The micromechanical model proposed by Grandidier has been fully validated for the T700GC/M21 material. In order to use the model, however, several pieces of experimental data are required.

Firstly, the analysis of the microstructure has been performed to measure parameters related to the structural effect, such as the volume fraction of fibres and their radius, thanks to the analysis of CT scans. The distribution of fibre radii has been determined, yielding an average Weibull value of $r_f = 3.25 \mu\text{m}$ and a fibre volume ratio of $V_f = 56\%$. In a previous study, the mechanical properties of the fibres and the matrix were determined using an inverse method based on the Mori-Tanaka approach. This method was used to obtain the relevant mechanical properties measured at the ply scale, based on tensile tests performed on 0-ply, 90-ply and $[\pm 45]$ laminates. The values identified were $E_f = 240 \text{ GPa}$, $E_m = 3100 \text{ MPa}$, and $\nu_m = 0.3$.

Then, the plasticity of the matrix, which is modelled using a Ramberg-Osgood law, requires the identification of three parameters (τ_{UD}^y , G_{UD} , n_{UD}) at different temperatures. These parameters can be determined by inverse identification using tensile tests on a $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate tested at 20 °C, 70 °C and 120 °C at ONERA, as reported in Fig. 3 [20]. The tensile tests were performed at ONERA Lille in accordance with AITM1-002 [21], but with a displacement rate of 1 mm/s, which is consistent with the loading rate applied to the 0-ply compression tests. Longitudinal and transverse strain gauges were used to measure the in-plane shear strain in the tested specimens at different temperatures. The Ramberg-Osgood parameters for each temperature were identified independently using an automated identification method based on the simplex method [22] to calibrate the three parameters. It was observed that these three parameters evolve linearly as a function of temperature. Therefore, a first-order polynomial has been fitted to each of the three parameters to successfully describe the available experimental data at different temperatures, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Tensile test on $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates at different temperatures and comparison with simulated Ramberg-Osgood model predictions

The final parameter to identify is the initial misalignment of the fibres, which causes them to kink within the composite material. This value was determined using inverse identification in conjunction with a tensile test on a specific laminate that failed in compression. The identified value is $\phi_0 = 2^\circ$, which is consistent with data found in the literature [15,23].

Fig. 4a shows a successful comparison between experimental stress/strain curves at different temperatures and the predicted elastic nonlinear behaviour introduced in the OPFM model which is assumed to be insensitive to temperature. The details of the nonlinear elastic behaviour are given in [24]. Finally, Fig. 4b presents a comparison of the test results for 0 ply at different temperatures with the predictions of the identified micromechanical model. The evolution of strength with temperature is predicted very accurately from ambient temperature to 120°C. The decrease in strength with temperature is approximately -40% compared to ambient temperature, which is significant and must be considered in the design of composite structures.

Figure 4: Experimental and predicted a) longitudinal behavior and b) evolution of the longitudinal compressive strength of UD ply subjected to compression at different temperatures

3. BENDING TESTS ON UD PLY AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

3.1 Presentation of four-point bending test results on UD ply at different temperatures

The longitudinal compressive strength of 268 g/m² carbon/epoxy T700GC/M21 unidirectional plies has also been determined using classical four-point bending tests on 0° laminates. Several authors have indeed proposed using bending tests to overcome the challenges associated with compressive testing of unidirectional laminates. For a carbon/epoxy unidirectional ply, the longitudinal compressive strength is much lower than the longitudinal tensile strength. Therefore, three-point bending tests [25,26] and four-point bending tests [27] are useful for identifying compressive strength in the fibre direction.

Therefore, four-point bending tests have been performed on specimens constituted with 8 0-ply at ONERA Châtillon using an electromechanical testing machine with a maximum loading capacity of 150kN. The specimens measured 120×10×2.23 mm. The loading rate was fixed at 1 mm/min. The distance between the support spans is 100 mm, and the distance between the loading spans is 30 mm. The span radius has been set to 5 mm. The experimental device was introduced into a furnace that allowed a temperature to be applied ranging from -100°C to 500°C. Furthermore, a large window in the furnace door enables measurement of the strain field on one of the specimen's free edges, where a black-and-white speckle pattern has been applied. This is achieved using digital image correlation with Vic2D software, with one camera focused between the loading span to observe the failure pattern and another observing the global view of the setup to control the boundary conditions. The experimental setup is described in Fig. 5. Four-point bending tests were performed at different temperatures: 20 °C, 45 °C, 120 °C, 145 °C and 165 °C. Only one specimen was tested for each temperature studied.

Figure 5: Four-point bending tests performed in a furnace at different temperatures, from ambient temperature to 165°C.

The failure pattern has been analysed at different temperatures. At temperatures above 100°C, failure of the specimen is more progressive, with compressive fibre failure occurring between the loading spans. The measured strains at failure for these high temperatures are reported in Fig. 6. A typical failure pattern is observed at 120 °C, and these results can be considered valid. Linear evolution of apparent longitudinal strain at failure as a function of temperature is observed. However, at 20°C and 45°C, failure occurs prematurely within the loading spans. These strains at failure, which are also reported in Fig. 6, are not considered valid for the purposes of the following analysis. It is well known that four-point bending test set-ups generate high stress concentrations under the rollers, which can lead to local indentation and premature specimen failure.

To avoid this, some authors introduced polymer pads between the rollers and the specimens [23]. However, this necessitates the characterisation of the additional material's mechanical behaviour. To overcome this difficulty, an alternative bending device has been developed, which is presented in the next section.

Figure 6: Evolution of the longitudinal strain at failure as a function of the temperature considering test results from four-point bending and compressive with pivot tests.

3.2 Presentation of compression with pivot test on UD ply at ambient temperature

The compression with pivots testing device [28] enables bending loading to be generated by offsetting the mid-plane of the laminate with respect to the rotation axes of the pivots. This is an alternative to existing bending testing devices [11,14,29–31]. This device avoids local stress concentrations close to the jaws and the indentation issues experienced with the aforementioned testing set-ups. Furthermore, it enables direct observation of compressive failure in the surface plies of the laminate. Due to the use of a bending loading mode, the failure mechanism can be observed in the gauge section, which is far from the jaws.

Figure 7a shows an original experimental compression device with pivots. The concept involves applying uniform compression to a laminate plate that is clamped between two jaws with pivots. The eccentricity of a given test relates to the offset of the plate's mid-surface and imposes the compression-to-bending ratio. This is controlled by inserting a couple of wedges adequately into the jaws of the tabs. In the present study, large eccentricities equal to half the total thickness of the specimen being tested are used to obtain a quasi-pure bending moment in the gauge length.

Figure 7: a) Presentation of the compression with pivots experimental device, b) Failure pattern of the 16 0-ply subjected to bending loading

Bending tests on 16 0-ply specimens have been performed at ONERA Châtillon, but only at ambient temperature. The specimens measured 130 mm x 30 mm x 4.2 mm. Three specimens were tested. Different measurement techniques were used to improve understanding of the physical mechanisms involved and to obtain global and local information, as reported in Fig. 7a: (i) a LVDT sensor; (ii) acoustic emission to detect damage events during loading (no acoustic events were detected prior to final failure); (iii) strain gauges bonded to the upper and lower faces of the unnotched specimens to measure strain; and (iv) stereo digital image correlation (using the Vic3D system) on the two faces of the specimen painted with black-and-white speckles to measure in-plane strains on the outer surfaces, as shown in Fig. 6b, (v) post-mortem micrographs to study the failure pattern of the specimens. The distribution of fibre failure in tension and compression through the thickness can easily be observed in the post-mortem pictures since the grey colours correspond to different failure mechanisms. The evolution of the mid-plane during the tests is also clearly visible. Furthermore, failure occurs far from the jaws and can be considered a valid compressive fibre failure mode. The strain at failure on the compression face, measured with DIC and a strain gauge at ambient temperature, is -1.6%, with a covariance of 2.9%. This has been added to Fig. 6 (blue point) and should be considered instead of the test results at 20 °C and 45 °C obtained using four-point bending device. The evolution of the strain at failure appears to be linear again, with a -50% decrease in strain at failure for compression with a pivot test at ambient temperature compared to that measured in four-point bending tests at 165°C.

3.3 Analysis of the bending tests with the micromechanical model

The micromechanical model was applied to estimate the longitudinal compressive strength of bending tests carried out at different temperatures. The strain at failure was estimated by considering the elastic nonlinear behaviour mentioned in Section 2.2 and previously identified. It should be noted that the effective thickness considers the evolution of the middle plane during the bending test due to the hardening observed in longitudinal tension and the softening observed in longitudinal compression. Fig. 8 shows a comparison of the predicted and measured strain at failure obtained from the bending test. Initially, the predicted evolution of the failure strain appears slightly nonlinear and is consistent with the experimental data.

Figure 8: Predicted and measured evolution of the longitudinal strain at failure as a function of the temperature considering bending tests

The same identification has been used for the micromechanical model in order to predict the evolution of the longitudinal compressive strength (or longitudinal strain at failure) when 0-ply is subjected to compression or bending at different temperatures. The results obtained are promising.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study determined the longitudinal compressive strength of T700GC/M21 unidirectional carbon/epoxy plies by performing compression and bending tests at different temperatures (from ambient to 145 °C) and analysing the results using an original micromechanical approach.

The longitudinal compressive strength was determined from the results of standardised compression tests on sixteen 0-plyes at different temperatures. The longitudinal compressive strength and the associated strain at failure decreased linearly with temperature, dropping by -40% at 120°C. Furthermore, four-point bending tests were carried out on 8 0-plyes at different temperatures. The longitudinal strain was measured using digital image correlation to observe the specimen through a large window into the furnace. Once again, the evolution of the measured strain at failure is almost linear as a function of temperature, dropping by -50% at 145°C.

The micromechanical model proposed by Grandidier was used to determine the apparent longitudinal compressive strength of the ply. This model takes into account the nonlinearity of the matrix and was calibrated at different temperatures through the analysis of tensile tests on $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates, and the nonlinear behaviour in the fibre direction. Analysis of the various tests using the current failure approach has demonstrated consistency between the test data obtained at different temperatures, which is encouraging.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to DGA-TA for funding this experimental and numerical study.

REFERENCES

- [1] P.D. Soden, M.J. Hinton, A.S. Kaddour, A comparison of the predictive capabilities of current failure theories for composite laminates, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 58 (1998) 1225–1254.
- [2] MIL-HDBK-17-1F: Composite Materials Handbook, Volume 1 - Polymer Matrix Composites Guidelines for Characterization of Structural Materials, U.S. Department of Defence, 2002.
- [3] K. Hofer, P. Rao, A New Static Compression Fixture for Advanced Composite Materials, *J. Test. Eval.* 5 (1977) 278–283.
- [4] ASTM D3410 / D3410M - 16, Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials with Unsupported Gage Section by Shear Loading, 2016.
- [5] AECMA, AECMA standard EN-2850, Aerospace series carbon fibre thermosetting resin unidirectional laminates. Compression test parallel to fibre direction, 1997.
- [6] C. Soutis, J. Lee, C. Kong, Size effect on compressive strength of T300/924C carbon fibre-epoxy laminates, *Plast. Rubber Compos.* 31 (2002) 364–370.
- [7] ASTM D695-15, Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Rigid Plastics, 2015.
- [8] ASTM D6641 / D6641M-16, Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials Using a Combined Loading Compression (CLC) Test Fixture, 2016.
- [9] D. Adams, J. Welsh, The Wyoming Combined Loading Compression (CLC) Test Method, *J. Compos. Technol. Res.* 19 (1997) 123–133.
- [10] I.M. Daniel, H.M. Hsiao, Is there a thickness effect on compressive strength of unnotched composite laminates?, *Int. J. Fract.* 95 (1999) 143–158.
- [11] O. Allix, P. Ladeveze, E. Vittecoq, Modelling and identification of the mechanical behaviour of composite laminates in compression, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 51 (1994) 35–42.
- [12] T. Yokozeki, T. Ogasawara, T. Ishikawa, Nonlinear behavior and compressive strength of unidirectional and multidirectional carbon fiber composite laminates, *Compos. Part A* 37 (2006) 2069–2079.
- [13] S. Drapier, J.-C. Grandidier, M. Potier-Ferry, Towards a numerical model of the compressive strength for long fibre composites, *Eur. J. Mech. - ASolids* 18 (1999) 69–92.
- [14] J.-C. Grandidier, G. Ferron, M. Potier-Ferry, Microbuckling and strength in long-fiber composites: theory and experiments, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 29 (1992) 1753–1761.

- [15] J.-C. Grandidier, P. Casari, C. Jochum, A fibre direction compressive failure criterion for long fibre laminates at ply scale, including stacking sequence and laminate thickness effects, *Compos. Struct.* 94 (2012) 3799–3806. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.06.013>.
- [16] B. Budiansky, N.A. Fleck, Compressive failure of fibre composites, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 41 (1993) 183–211.
- [17] S. Drapier, C. Gardin, J.-C. Grandidier, M. Potier-Ferry, Structure effect and microbuckling, 9th Fr. Natl. Colloq. *Compos. Mater.* 56 (1996) 861–867. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538\(96\)00033-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(96)00033-4).
- [18] C. Gardin, J.C. Grandidier, M. Potier-Ferry, Homogenized models for the modelling of instability in long fibre media, *Rev. Mec. Appliquée Théorique* 1 (2002) 171–203.
- [19] M.R. Wisnom, J.W. Atkinson, Constrained buckling tests show increasing compressive strain to failure with increasing strain gradient, *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf. Inc. Compos. Compos. Manuf.* 28 (1997) 964.
- [20] J. Berthe, M. Brieu, E. Deletombe, Thermo-viscoelastic modelling of organic matrix composite behaviour – Application to T700GC/M21, *Mech. Mater.* 81 (2015) 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2014.10.005>.
- [21] AITM, AITM standard 1-0002, Fibre reinforced plastics - Determination of in-plane shear properties (+45 tensile test), 1998.
- [22] J.C. Lagarias, J.A. Reeds, M.H. Wright, P.E. Wright, Convergence properties of the Nelder-Mead simplex method in low dimensions, *SIAM J. Optim.* 9 (1998) 112–147. <https://doi.org/10.1137/S1052623496303470>.
- [23] P.-Y. Mechin, V. Keryvin, J.-C. Grandidier, D. Glehen, An experimental protocol to measure the parameters affecting the compressive strength of CFRP with a fibre micro-buckling failure criterion, *Compos. Struct.* 211 (2019) 154–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.12.026>.
- [24] F. Laurin, N. Carrere, J.-F. Maire, Strength analysis methods for high stress gradient parts in composite structures ensuring design office requirements, *ProcIMEchE PartG JAerospace Eng.* 225 (2011) 291–301.
- [25] N. Carbajal, F. Mujika, Determination of compressive strength of unidirectional composites by three-point bending tests, *Polym. Test.* 28 (2009) 150–156.
- [26] N. Carbajal, F. Mujika, Determination of longitudinal compressive strength of long fiber composites by three-point bending of [0°_m/90°_n/0°_p] cross-ply laminated strips, *Polym. Test.* 28 (2009) 618–626.
- [27] P.J. Callus, The effects of hole-size and environment on the mechanical behaviour of a quasi-isotropic AS4/3501-6 laminate in tension, compression and bending, Defence Science and Technology Organisation of Australian Government, 2007.
- [28] F. Laurin, C. Julien, P. Paulmier, Damage and strength analysis of open-hole laminated plates under tensile, compressive and bending loadings, in: 2016: pp. 1–8.
- [29] M.R. Wisnom, On the Increase in Fracture Energy with Thickness in Delamination of Unidirectional Glass Fibre-Epoxy with Cut Central Plies, *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.* 11 (1992) 909.
- [30] M.R. Wisnom, T. Reynolds, N. Gwilliam, Reduction in interlaminar shear strength by discrete and distributed voids, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 56 (1996) 101.
- [31] C. Hochard, J. Payan, O. Montagnier, Design and computation of laminated composite structures, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 65 (2005) 474.